

Recommendation 4	Mean	Median	Lowest Score	Highest Score
<p>Robot-assisted movement training to improve motor function and mobility after stroke in combination with conventional therapy may be considered</p> <p>56 33 14 37 42 14 37 50 79</p> <p>1 2 3 4 5 6 7 8 9</p> <p>lower level of applicability higher level of applicability</p>	5	5	1	9

Recommendation 5	Mean	Median	Lowest Score	Highest Score
<p>People with stroke who are able to walk (albeit with the assistance of other people or assistive devices) and who wish to improve their mobility at any stage after stroke should be offered access to equipment to enable intensive walking training such as treadmills or electromechanical gait trainers. To achieve this, training needs to be at 60-85% heart rate reserve (by adjustment of inclination or speed) for at least 40 minutes, three times a week for 10 weeks.</p> <p>81 23 14 23 79 22 13 41 66</p> <p>1 2 3 4 5 6 7 8 9</p> <p>lower level of applicability higher level of applicability</p>	4	5	1	9

Recommendation 6	Mean	Median	Lowest Score	Highest Score
<p>Practice walking with either a treadmill (with or without body-weight support) or overground walking exercise training combined with conventional rehabilitation may be reasonable for recovery of walking function.</p> <p>9 9 28 14 18 18 74 37 155</p> <p>1 2 3 4 5 6 7 8 9</p> <p>lower level of applicability higher level of applicability</p>	7	8	1	9

Recommendation 7	Mean	Median	Lowest Score	Highest Score
<p>incorporating cardiovascular exercise and strengthening interventions is reasonable to consider for recovery of gait capacity and gait-related mobility tasks.</p> <p>9 5 14 28 23 23 70 70 120</p> <p>1 2 3 4 5 6 7 8 9</p> <p>lower level of applicability higher level of applicability</p>	7	8	1	9

Recommendation 8	Mean	Median	Lowest Score	Highest Score
<p>Biofeedback, in the form of visual and/or auditory signals to indicate unequal weight bearing and timing, can be used to enhance gait training and improve functional recovery.</p> <p>0 0 0 0 0 0 0 232 130</p> <p>1 2 3 4 5 6 7 8 9</p> <p>lower level of applicability higher level of applicability</p>	8	7	8	9

Recommendation 9	Mean	Median	Lowest Score	Highest Score
<p>Virtual reality training (such as non-immersive technologies) could be considered as an adjunct to conventional gait training.</p> <p>13 5 28 42 28 28 51 51 115</p> <p>1 2 3 4 5 6 7 8 9</p> <p>lower level of applicability higher level of applicability</p>	5	5	1	9

Recommendation 10	Mean	Median	Lowest Score	Highest Score
<p>Rhythmic auditory stimulation (RAS) should be considered for improving gait parameters in stroke patients, including gait velocity, cadence, stride length, and gait symmetry.</p> <p style="text-align: center;"> 41 14 20 46 37 51 51 32 70 1 2 3 4 5 6 7 8 9 lower level of applicability higher level of applicability </p>	5	6	1	9

Recommendation 11	Mean	Median	Lowest Score	Highest Score
<p>Group therapy with circuit training is a reasonable approach to improve walking.</p> <p style="text-align: center;"> 0 138 224 1 2 3 4 5 6 7 8 9 lower level of applicability higher level of applicability </p>	8	9	8	9

Recommendation 12	Mean	Median	Lowest Score	Highest Score
<p>Mental Practice should be considered as an adjunct to lower extremity motor retraining.</p> <p style="text-align: center;"> 18 9 32 23 47 47 47 56 83 1 2 3 4 5 6 7 8 9 lower level of applicability higher level of applicability </p>	6	7	1	9

Recommendation 16	Mean	Median	Lowest Score	Highest Score
<p>Functional electrical stimulation (FES) should be used to improve strength and function (gait) in selected patients, but the effects may not be sustained.</p> <p style="text-align: center;"> 37 15 24 32 60 70 46 60 18 1 2 3 4 5 6 7 8 9 lower level of applicability higher level of applicability </p>	5	6	1	9

Recommendation 17	Mean	Median	Lowest Score	Highest Score
<p>The person with stroke, their family/carers, and clinicians in all settings should be trained in the safe application and use of orthoses and electrical stimulation devices.</p> <p style="text-align: center;"> 0 101 107 154 1 2 3 4 5 6 7 8 9 lower level of applicability higher level of applicability </p>	8	8	7	9

Recommendation 18	Mean	Median	Lowest Score	Highest Score
<p>Stroke services should have local protocols and agreements in place to ensure specialist assessment, evaluation, and follow-up is available for long-term functional electrical stimulation use.</p> <p style="text-align: center;"> 32 9 14 14 51 46 37 56 103 1 2 3 4 5 6 7 8 9 lower level of applicability higher level of applicability </p>	6	7	1	9

Recommendation 19	Mean	Median	Lowest Score	Highest Score
<p>People with limited mobility after stroke should be assessed for, provided with, and trained to use appropriate mobility aids, including a wheelchair, to enable safe independent mobility.</p> <p style="text-align: center;"> 5 0 9 24 32 18 24 74 176 1 2 3 4 5 6 7 8 9 lower level of applicability higher level of applicability </p>	7	8	1	9

Recommendation 20	Mean	Median	Lowest Score	Highest Score
<p>People with stroke who are mobile should be assessed for real-world walking such as road crossing, walking on uneven ground, over distances and inclines. This should include assessment of the impact of dual tasking, neglect, vision, and confidence in busy environments.</p> <p style="text-align: center;"> 9 5 28 23 37 32 37 32 159 1 2 3 4 5 6 7 8 9 lower level of applicability higher level of applicability </p>	6	8	1	9

Recommendation 21	Mean	Median	Lowest Score	Highest Score
<p>Clinicians should not use risk assessment protocols that limit training for fear of cardiovascular or other adverse events, given the good safety record of repetitive gait training however it is delivered.</p> <p style="text-align: center;"> 56 9 32 28 46 60 37 37 57 1 2 3 4 5 6 7 8 9 lower level of applicability higher level of applicability </p>	5	6	1	9